

CMIP7 Use Case (as part of WP4 EDS Plus funding)

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Objectives:

List of initial objectives:

To understand how CMIP data is used and going to be used by the UK research community. What features of CMIP attracts people to use it and what are the obstacles that people run into when using and accessing CMIP data. How the UK research community engages in the CMIP development process. What tools and workflows would be valuable to improve CMIP data access and useability, and to capture the data requirements of the scientific community as we prepare for CMIP7.

To what extent have the objectives been realised:

We have spoken with a number of CMIP data users at various research institutions and points in their career to gain an understanding of what the community feels could be improved about the CMIP data service and obstacles to CMIP data access. The discussions were largely oriented around experiences with data from previous CMIPs and expectations for CMIP7. A question possibly missing from the interviews would have been to ask directly how we best move forward to capture the data requirements of the scientific community as we prepare for CMIP7. However, CMIP is currently working to capture this information via the CMIP task teams as preparations are made for CMIP7.

Collaborations:

Internal to the project:

Internal collaborations were between the team at CEDA

Externally:

We reached out to a total of 18 researchers across 6 institutions and 7 early career researchers. From this we interviewed 7 researchers and 4 ECRs from the UK Met Office and universities of Cambridge, KIT (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology), Leeds, Oxford and Reading.

Summary of approach

(summarise how you have gone about the research, methods used, etc.):

We initially reached out to researchers from a number of institutions that we knew had links to CMIP data to ask them to talk with us about their experiences.

The interviews lasted about an hour and we asked questions around 5 key themes:

- How CMIP data is used by the UK research community.
- Positive features that attract people to use CMIP data.
- What makes it difficult to use CMIP data.
- Opportunities for the research community to better engage with CMIP.
- Anything else they would like us to know about.

We also asked in both the initial email and the interviews for suggestions of other colleagues to contact that work with CMIP data, including specifically early career researchers. This '**snowballing technique**' helped us to reach out to a wider range of specifically selected people.

Where availability aligned we did interviews in pairs and we wrote up a report after each interview.

What outputs have been produced (prototypes, reports, papers):

We have produced write-up reports of each interview under the 5 key themes described above. That is, 7 interview reports in total and a synthesis document bringing together all the responses and common key themes. A collection of enlivening quotes, useful phrases about CMIP and JASMIN resources.

Findings:

Our overall reflections from the work (what worked, what did not work, overall lessons learned):

What worked well:

- We found rich information from just interviewing a few specific people. We also found that even with this relatively small sample size, the same comments were appearing across the interviews
- Interviews with a couple of people at a time meant they bounced off each other and shared common experiences. There was also instances where the interviewees learnt from each other about services and data available
- Asking researchers with existing links if they could suggest ECR's to talk to meant we were able to gain the perspective of people fairly new to CMIP data who faced different challenges
- People were keen to talk about their experiences and make suggestions for improvement. They were also very positive about JASMIN and the existing services provided.

What did not work:

- Short timeframe over the holiday period meant we did not have as much time as we would have liked to invest in reaching out to people and sending reminders. It also meant it was difficult to get hold of people (due to A/L etc.)

Overall lessons learnt:

- Though the CMIP community involves a diverse range of research areas, the experiences, issues and suggestions put forward from the CMIP data users we spoke to often overlapped.

- 'Snowballing technique' of asking a contact for suggestions of other contacts is an effective way to reach key people in a research network who we did not know already
- JASMIN is an essential resource for scientists working with CMIP data in the UK for both data access and facilitating data analysis
- A centralised place for technical information about models, variables would make the data accessible to more users and save users a lot of time
- As data gets large, specifically for CMIP, centralised compute centres like JASMIN becomes necessary to access and analyse the data
- Data accessible via the archive is significantly easier to access than pulling the data directly from the ESGF node
- Detailed metadata contained within the files themselves (in the CMORized Net-CDF format) saves users a lot of time trying to scrape the information from many separated resources, increasing usability of the data

Recommendations for the next phase of EDS commissioning:

- Reaching out to members new to the community (e.g. early career researchers) as well as experienced users for ideas and suggestions in shaping the development of the EDS for a different perspective.
- In person conversations with representative members of the community (including ECRs) keen to share their experiences and ideas for preparing the EDS for CMIP7.
- More community consultation within the UK about which CMIP data should be archived with the EDS. Currently variables are prioritised for the IPCC AR6 but this could be extended to e.g. the needs of large NERC national capability projects. Perhaps a comparison between CMIP variable data usage between variables archived at CEDA and variables pulled by scientists from the ESGF node to check we are archiving the CMIP data most used by the UK science community.

- A set of tools/python scripts provided at the top level for users to run quality checks on data they download to catch errors in data
- A parallel space to the CMIP data archive hosted by the EDS for the community where people share scripts for accessing data and data analysis, catching errors etc.
- Training for use of JASMIN for data analysis and best practices. In several interviews it was highlighted that they learnt by 'trial and error' or from colleagues but would like to optimise their code and analysis techniques. As well as lowering the bar for climate data analysis, this training will help scope the needs of the CMIP community to make data available accessible to more users.
- Better help documentation for pointing to model and variable information, and useful resources for first time CMIP (or more generally EDS) users. A theme across the interviews was a need for a common place for information.
- Errors in CMIP data was a common issue raised and many suggested a reporting system for flagging these errors as they are found either in a forum or at the directory level in the archive would be useful and would encourage user engagement
- Better batch download tools e.g. to download all data across models from one variable
- Funding for implementing the improvements to CMIP data access proposed in the interviews and communicating these improvements.

Recommendations for the wider objective of developing a commons approach for environmental assets:

- Bringing valuable information about data into one clearly findable place for simplicity. It seems that as CMIP is such a huge and global resource, the information necessary for using the different datasets is inevitably spread over

many places making it difficult to find, particularly with analysis using a number of models.

Some nice quotes:

“JASMIN, it’s like the air, if it went away it would be a real problem”

“Access by disk is by far the best solution”

“CMIP is the best thing there is for understanding climate change on a global scale and capturing the full range of model uncertainty”

“It’s been transformative” (about JASMIN)

“JASMIN is enabling loads and loads of science that would not otherwise get done.”

“There’s a lot of data ‘a zoo of MIPs’ within CMIP to investigate”

“Cf conventions are fantastic”

Synthesis

The complete feedback we received from our interviewees has been collated in a [synthesis report](#).